

DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETENCIES FOR STUDENTS' SELF - STUDY IN A CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *This article reveals the credit-module education system in higher education institutions and identifies the development of competencies for independent learning as a pedagogical process problem. Autonomous education is the desire and capacity for knowledge acquisition that students develop via deliberate, creative inquiry. According to didactics, students' autonomous completion of a cognitive activity that reflects a problem results in new information and approaches to problem-solving. This is one way that independent education manifests itself.*

Keywords: *aptitude, didactic, credit module, cognitive, component, category, anatomy, and motivation.*

Models and techniques for the development of competencies for students' independent education in the Balonian educational system are being applied to the educational process. In the credit and module system in international educational institutions, personnel training for the world's quality labor market, and the development of competencies for students' independent education raise the level of training. Competitive credit module education systems, free professional specialists' operation for the benefit of society's economic sectors, the development of professional and pedagogical training through professional and communicative competencies, and systematic efforts to improve higher education institutions where the credit module education system is implemented are all present in developed nations like the United States, Great Britain, England, Germany, France, China, Japan, South Korea, and Russia. History of Education: When it comes to recognizing the essence of students' independent education, there are a number of ways that may be seen in the educational orientation of historical scientific instruction. While some authors prioritize the activity side of this topic, others focus more on psychological

components. According to I.Ya. Lerner, autonomous education is the desire and capacity for knowledge acquisition that students develop via deliberate, creative inquiry. According to didactics, students' autonomous completion of a cognitive activity that reflects a problem results in new information and approaches to problem-solving. This is one way that independent education manifests itself. In addition to being an expression of autonomous learning, cognitive activities "serve as a pedagogical tool for its formation" [Lerner,1992]. Instead of basing his methodology on his own ideas, the researcher adopts an activity-based approach. According to N.A.Polovnikova and L.P. Aristova, the educational direction of history education in the credit module education system takes a different approach to the problem of developing independent education of students in the teaching of historical sciences by taking into account the personal qualities of students and favoring a psychological and didactic approach to solving the existing problem. They do study on the prosthetic component of students' cognitive (cognitive) activity in their work. [Polovnikova,1977] According to N.A. Polovnikova, an individual possesses attributes such as preparedness (capacity and aspiration) to do tasks independently and acquire meaningful knowledge. This is what is meant by independent education. The presence of internal motives in addition to the matching motives that comprise the stimulating side of Independent Education determines the student's desire for cognitive activity, or more specifically, the desire to learn new information. Ability is predicated on prior knowledge and the absorption of active techniques. The substance of independent education is known as auxiliary knowledge, and the activities that are used to acquire information are their procedural or technical aspects [Polovnikova,1977]. According to T.I. Shamova, one of the primary integrative qualities connected to the development of a system of knowledge and activity methods, as well as their application and assimilation of new ones, as well as voluntary actions, is the education of positive qualities for an individual's reading and learning. This attribute in an individual is defined, in the absence of outside influences, as the willingness and capacity to learn new things, pick up new skills, and find solutions to difficulties related to learning [Shamova,2002]. A person's capacity for independent learning is shaped and developed as a personality trait by a variety of interdependent internal and external forces. Internal elements include the student's personality traits (inclinations, willpower, temperament, etc.), life experiences, enhanced learning processes, knowledge that has been obtained, and methods of acquiring it. The social milieu in which he lives, the educational process, and the entire society around the University of the pedagogical higher education institution are examples of external variables. The appearance, which is regarded as a

system of internal formations and actual acts for self-education, is what is meant by independent education. One characteristic of an independent learner is that they possess a set of skills, knowledge, and behaviors that help them to both independently acquire general and specialized knowledge in addition to carrying out the process of learning knowledge, abilities, and credentials to address significant personal issues as a contributing member of society. A person's indicated character results from his or her self-development, which eventually aims to mold the learner into the type of person they want to be in society. The phenomenon's social aspect is shown in how it stimulates and is perceived as helping people enhance their knowledge and abilities. One significant component of independent education is the level of knowledge acquired prior to a given time; the complex of skills necessary for independent knowledge acquisition reflects its working composition; aspirations are expressed as a desire to read and learn in order to enhance one's moral, mental, or physical attributes and are directed toward the accomplishment of a socially constructed objective; abilities, on the other hand, identify innate tendencies. It is widely acknowledged that there are three primary components to the instructional orientation of history education for students in higher education institutions' credit module systems: volitional, meaningful-practical, and motivation (stimulating). Naturally, the reasons behind the goal-directed action are linked to the manifestation of the activity of acquiring independent information. On the other hand, the meaningful-practical component entails a student-mastered system of prioritized knowledge and mastering techniques. Only when a student has a certain system of priority knowledge and is able to master it independently will their constant desire to learn new things and to support the integration of new techniques of activity come true. The stimulating and meaningful-practical aspect of students' independent education in the study of historical subjects is directly tied to volitional processes within the framework of higher education institutions' credit-based educational systems [Shamova, 2002]. Students must act in a certain volitional way in addition to desire in order to accomplish the goal. Activities that support independent knowledge acquisition as well as independent knowledge acquisition are closely related to the idea of independent education. Self-education activities can also become a person's need for independent knowledge, that is, a source of independent educational activities. Important conditions for such rotation are: duration of stimulation, its consistency and intensity. Thus, the Independent Education of students is largely associated with psychological support, the formation (consciousness) of the needs for mastering social and new knowledge and skills, practical preparation of students for the

implementation of independent educational activities, the level of influence of the social environment and the corresponding level of knowledge.

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